

Factors Influencing the Digital Transformation of Tourism Enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: Digital transformation is inevitable for Vietnamese tourism businesses after the COVID-19 epidemic and will determine their existence and development moving forward. However, the digital transformation process in tourism businesses also has many problems, requiring more synchronous recommendations in the future.

Objective: This study aims to analyse the factors influencing the digital transformation of tourism enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Methodology: The researchers used a descriptive survey to achieve the aim of the study. A convenience sample of 350 respondents was used to evaluate the proposed model's fit and test hypotheses using structural equation modelling to assess the factors impacting the digital transformation of tourism enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Result: The results indicate that staff capacity, business goals, corporate culture, technological platform, and government support policy significantly impact the digital transformation of tourism businesses.

Conclusion: These results provide practical insights for advancing digital transformation in tourism enterprises, especially in the context of rapid technological changes and the stringent demands of the market.

Unique Contribution: This study has provided empirical evidence for understanding the current trends on the growth of the tourism sector within the content of the Asian economy.

Key Recommendation: Managers and tourism enterprises should implement robust communication strategies, raise public awareness about the benefits of digital transformation, and help improve customer experience to promote convenience and flexibility in the booking, tour booking, and payment process.

Keywords: Digital transformation; tourist business; policy recommendations; Ho Chi Minh City

Introduction

Digital transformation (DT) refers to the restructuring of business models and processes through technology-driven approaches aimed at delivering new value to customers and adapting to the digital economy (Wang et al., 2024). Since 2010, the digital infrastructure, including the Internet of Things, big data, artificial intelligence, and mobile technology, has significantly transformed operations within the tourism industry, drastically changing tourism communication methods and how data is collected and analysed to make optimal stakeholder decisions. The products, services, customer experiences, and destination marketing within tourism have all been affected by digital technology. DT is increasingly common within businesses, raising numerous concerns for researchers and practitioners (Gerhart & Feng, 2021).

Digital technology has altered the business environment and impacted enterprises in the tourism industry. Digital transformation offers opportunities and creative solutions within tourism, enabling customers to independently plan trips, make online bookings, book supplementary services via mobile devices, and simultaneously provide feedback and share experiences (Imtiaz & Kim, 2019). However, the DT process is still slow, especially for businesses in the tourism sector, due to a lack of resources and the insufficient capacity of the workforce to keep up with these trends. Tourism is an interdisciplinary sector that includes transportation, accommodation, restaurants, and personal services. Each industry faces unique opportunities and challenges when adopting digital technology. These differences include human resource capabilities, access to financial and non-financial resources, and digital skills awareness. The challenges and opportunities businesses face in the tourism industry become more complex, affected, and extended within the business ecosystem and at the destination level. Therefore, it is essential to design integrated structures, policies, and specific action strategies for each phase to ensure success in the digital transformation process.

Ho Chi Minh City is undergoing a significant transformation in the tourism sector by applying digital transformation and continuously upgrading its technological infrastructure. This includes updating tourism information on digital platforms such as Google Maps and Google Earth, using 3D/360 technology to connect Ho Chi Minh City with 62 provinces and cities, offering content in five languages (Vietnamese, English, Chinese, French, and Spanish), and promoting the city's tourism destinations via online channels and social media (Ho Chi Minh City Department of Tourism, 2024). For enterprises in the tourism sector, the city regularly organises conferences to promote digital transformation, aiming to guide and support businesses in better managing and utilising data and accessing customers more effectively via digital marketing channels with lower costs and higher efficiency. However, the digital transformation in the tourism industry also faces significant challenges, with many tourism businesses confronting resource shortages, including financial resources, technological infrastructure, and a limited pool of highly skilled information technology (IT) professionals. The initial investment costs of adopting new technologies can be substantial. The challenges, such as cultural barriers, data shortages, the leadership vision, and resistance to change, exist. Therefore, the study's objectives are to analyse the factors influencing the digital transformation of tourism enterprises and provide management implications to promote successful digital transformation.

Literature Review

Digital transformation

Digital transformation is the overall and comprehensive change of individuals and organisations in their way of life, working, and production methods based on digital technologies, and digital transformation has no universal concept (Parvez et al., 2022). Digital transformation involves using cloud computing, sensor technology, and big data to generate new products or business models. Digital transformation is the deliberate and ongoing digital evolution of a company, business model, idea process, or methodology, both strategically and tactically (Wang et al., 2024). These definitions show that digital transformation uses advanced digital technologies like cloud computing, big data, the Internet of Things (Iot), and others to change business models, create new products, create new business opportunities, and improve organisational performance. Digital transformation needs a mindset shift, reorganization of people, data, processes, and technology adoption to create new value.

The process of digital transformation in tourism enterprises

Digital transformation will modify organisational structures, improve customer experiences, optimise internal and external relationships, and create new business models. Digital transformation has several benefits for tourism businesses and the sector. Kimbu et al. (2023) claim digital transformation will boost business operations. Companies need many resources for digital transformation (Wang et al., 2024). Digital transformation digitises industrial data, links it to other economic sectors, improves tourism products and services, and lets firms proactively manage staff performance and productivity. It adds value to corporate processes. Companies work more efficiently when tourism business processes become more open. Customers have more substantial, more timely relationships and better service. Digital transformation improves workforce quality, information technology skills, smart tourism, tourism marketing, business restructuring for sustainable growth, competitive capacity, revenue, regional business connections, and international tourism cooperation.

Technology organisation environment framework

The technology organisation environment (TOE) framework includes technology (T), organisation (O), and environment (E). This theoretical framework describes the entire corporate innovation process. It is an organisational-level paradigm that blends technological, organisational, and environmental elements to influence the adoption of firm innovation (Kimbu et al., 2023). Technologies relevant to the business, both those already in use and those available but untapped, are technology considerations. Existing technologies constrain a company's technological progress, making them vital to adoption (Parvez et al., 2022). Outside the corporation, innovations are gradual, architectural, or radical. Low-risk incremental innovations add features or versions of current technology, encouraging rapid organizational change. Modest change results from architectural advances that blend existing ideas or technologies. However, radical innovations differ significantly from conventional technology and methods.

Organizational characteristics affect internal communication, size, and resources. Strategy formulation and innovation depend on senior leadership. Many studies show that larger companies integrate innovations better. There are various opinions that organizational scale boosts innovation. Industry structure influences innovation, with fierce rivalry driving it. Skilled labour and

technological services boost innovation. Government laws affect creativity both positively and negatively. Government constraints on an industry often force enterprises to innovate.

Theoretical framework and hypothesis development

Digital transformation lies in focusing on the transformation aspect rather than the digital aspect itself. This requires flexibility in systems, processes, structures, leadership, human resources, and the appropriate mindset and culture (Wang et al., 2024). The role of digital transformation is to optimise operational systems, enabling organisations to achieve differentiation and create high value for sustainable competition.

Businesses face three main digital transformation concerns. First is the change in operational processes caused by electronic data exchange systems, which save time and boost efficiency. Second, changing the business model to produce new value involves changing operations. Finally, it improves customer experiences, which builds favourable consumer impressions through business-customer interactions. The digital transformation of firms has three stages. Strategic orientation requires firms to use technology to improve customer experiences and meet goals. Businesses use readily available or affordable resources at this level. In the second step, business model transformation, digital technology is applied broadly, and corporate functions are integrated. Management model adjustments to improve operational efficiency are standard in this stage. Third, management capability transformation integrates and synchronises business and management systems. Real-time information sharing across departments improves business management and execution. Instead of only technical difficulties, digital transformation should focus on broad aspects, requiring firms to adapt their systems, structures, processes, and people resources with the right mentality and culture. Technology, organisational strategy, leadership, culture, and talent are needed for digital transformation (Gerhart & Feng, 2021).

The policy potential and conditions shed light on Vietnam's tourist sector's digital revolution. These studies show how digital change boosts economic growth, especially in tourism. They demonstrate that digital transformation is a trend and a challenge for the Vietnamese tourism sector and enterprises and offer ideas to improve its efficacy. Therefore, identifying what needs to change and implementing it are crucial to success. Digital transformation is tied to strategy and digital culture, so firms should address consumer interactions and internal process efficiencies. Many studies show that organizational culture and change affect performance, but their effect on digital transformation in enterprises is unclear (Singh et al., 2020). Vaska et al. (2021) suggest studying how culture affects digital change. Other elements, including workers, corporate objectives, and government support, affect tourism enterprises' digital transformation performance, and more empirical studies are needed to help stakeholders design suitable policies.

The relationship between employee capacity and digital transformation

In the digital transformation process, staff play a crucial role, especially in the tourism sector, where the workforce must adapt to the changes driven by this transformation (Solberg et al., 2020). To effectively engage in digital transformation, staff must perform tasks more quickly, accurately, and efficiently. Staff readiness to embrace change is essential for the success of the digital transformation process. Numerous instances demonstrate that digital transformation fails when employees fail to meet new requirements or resist change despite implementing technical systems

based on best practices (Rousseau & Have, 2022). Based on this, the following hypothesis is proposed: H1 in Figure 1.

The relationship between business goals and digital transformation

Digital transformation involves proactively adjusting the business strategy to align with digital capabilities to leverage technology (Kindermann et al., 2021) effectively. The strategy shapes the goals, scope, and implementation roadmap, guiding the digital transformation process toward success. The goals of digital transformation provide opportunities for businesses to create new value based on existing resources. Zapata et al. (2020) evaluated the alignment of maturity models during the digital transformation process and the role of digital transformation in supporting the production of innovative products and proposed H2, as shown in Figure 1.

The relationship between organizational culture and digital transformation

Organisational culture is expressed through the organisation's values, beliefs, principles, and communication methods (Chaniyas et al., 2019; Warner & Wäger, 2019), while digital transformation represents the cultural change occurring within the company (Mergel et al., 2019). Digital transformation requires an organizational culture focused on verifying and sharing data. This demands high transparency in business and operational processes and a data-driven mindset among employees. Furthermore, digital transformation may lead to cultural conflicts between younger, tech-savvy employees with limited experience and older employees with extensive experience in traditional business practices, but who are outdated in technology. The following hypothesis is proposed: H3 in Figure 1.

The relationship between technology platforms and digital transformation

Digital transformation changes the structure of jobs, job roles, and workplace requirements (Parvez et al., 2022). Digital connectivity enables the formation of interdisciplinary work teams across the entire organisation. In this context, the traditional hierarchical work structure is gradually being phased out, creating new opportunities beyond the boundaries of the enterprise. The digital workplace must be adaptive, principled, imaginative, and location-independent. Therefore, the use of technology in current business operations will significantly influence the ability future, as proposed in H4 in Figure 1.

The relationship between government support policies and digital transformation

Government support significantly influences digital transformation, especially in developing countries (Bhardwaj et al., 2021). Government support for the digital transformation process is reflected in policies that invest in technological infrastructure, skilled labour, and the commitment to supporting businesses (Hussain et al., 2020). Legal and policy support, along with the government's financial infrastructure, positively impact the technological adoption activities of firms and proposed H5 in Figure 1.

Source: Proposal of the authors

Figure 1: Conceptual model for factors influencing the digital transformation of tourism enterprises

Figure 1 shows that there are five factors influencing the digital transformation of tourism enterprises, including: (1) Staff capacity (SC), (2) Business goals (BG), (3) Corporate culture (CC), (4) Technology platform (TP), (5) Government support policy (GS), (6) Digital transformation (DT).

Research Methods

Measurements

The following measuring scales were changed to match employee abilities: SC (Singhdong et al., 2021); BG (Zapata, 2020); CC (Parvez, 2022); TP and GS (Chen, 2021); and DT (Kimbu, 2023). Hair et al. (2018) recommended a sample size five times the number of observed variables. The theoretical study model has 30 observed variables; 150 samples are needed for analysis (30*5).

Data collection procedure

To make surveys more accessible, this study used convenience sampling with online and face-to-face methods. The research concept variables were measured using a 5-point Likert scale. The research team used convenience sampling with a 5:1 sample-to-variable ratio. Therefore, the minimal sample size was computed as $N \geq 5 * x$, where N is the sample size and x is the total number of observed variables. Hair et al. (2018) recommend one observed variable per five samples. Thus, the theoretical model requires 150 samples for the 30 observed variables. A minimum sample size of above 150 is sufficient for the research. Online surveys were sent to 350 Ho Chi Minh City tourism businesses. Verification and filtering yielded 350 valid survey responses. Data was analyzed using SPSS 20.0 and AMOS 20.0. Before encoding, cleaning, and data analysis, questionnaires that did not satisfy the criteria were removed.

Data analysis method

To determine the factors influencing the digital transformation of tourism firms in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, SPSS 25.0 was used to analyse the survey data objectively and accurately. Variables with item-total correlation values below 0.3 were omitted from Cronbach's Alpha reliability testing for scale internal consistency. We used exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to

evaluate the scales' appropriateness, using the KMO test ($0.5 \leq KMO \leq 1$) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Sig. < 0.05). After retaining factors with an Eigenvalue ≥ 1 , the variance explained had to reach 50%. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) also examines the links between observable variables and latent components. Assess model fit using Chi-square (χ^2) indices to determine goodness-of-fit. It should be non-significant ($p > 0.05$). Comparative Fit Index - CFI ≥ 0.90 indicates a strong fit. Tucker-Lewis Index - TLI ≥ 0.90 indicates a good fit. A reasonable match is marked by an RMSEA of < 0.08 . The SRMR < 0.08 is ideal. To determine convergent validity, evaluate each construct's AVE ≥ 0.50 . Finally, discriminant validity verifies concept distinction using the Fornell-larger criterion.

Study Results

Descriptive statistics

The demographic composition of the sample includes a nearly equal distribution of gender, with 50.6% (177) male participants and 49.4% (173) female participants. In terms of business size, the majority of respondents represent small businesses (35.4%, 124 participants), followed by medium-sized businesses (34.6%, 121 participants), and large businesses (30.0%, 105 participants). This distribution reflects a balanced gender representation and is relatively even spread across different business sizes. The total sample size consists of 350 participants, ensuring a comprehensive overview of the target population in the study.

Testing the reliability of the scale

The reliability of the measurement scales used to assess the constructs in the theoretical research model was tested. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of testing scale reliability

Code	Initial variable	Retained variable	Cronbach's alpha
SC:	SC1, SC2, SC3, SC4, SC5	SC1, SC2, SC3, SC4	0.713
BG:	BG1, BG2, BG3, BG4, BG5	BG1, BG2, BG3, BG4	0.714
CC:	CC1, CC2, CC3, CC4, CC5, CC6	CC2, CC3, CC5, CC6	0.726
TP:	TP1, TP2, TP3, TP4, TP5	TP1, TP3, TP4, TP5	0.720
GS:	GS1, GS2, GS3, GS4	GS1, GS2, GS3, GS4	0.762
DT:	DT1, DT2, DT3, DT4, DT5	DT1, DT2, DT3, DT4, DT5	0.920

Source: Data analysis results of the authors

Table 1 shows that the analysis results indicate that, after excluding the observed variables SC5, BG5, CC1, CC4, and TP2 due to their failure to meet the analytical criteria, the remaining scales exhibited Cronbach's Alpha coefficients greater than 0.7, thus meeting the required standards.

Exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis

Multiple linked elements affect Ho Chi Minh City tourism businesses' digital transformation (DT). Tourism businesses must improve their corporate culture, leverage government support policies, invest in advanced technology platforms, link business goals with digital strategies, and increase staff capacity to adapt to the digital economy. Prioritized by impact, these criteria offer actionable

insights for sustainable digital transformation. Structural equation modelling was employed to test the research hypotheses based on the results from the CFA. All the research constructs and their corresponding observed variables were subjected to a simultaneous oblique rotation within a factor analysis model to test the convergent and discriminant validity of all the measurement scales. The oblique rotation method in EFA is recommended when research hypotheses are tested using a structural equation model. The results indicated that the factors achieved both convergent and discriminant validity. However, the observed variables SC5, BG5, CC1, CC4, and TP2 were excluded from further analyses due to their failure to meet the validation criteria. The Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted using AMOS 25.0 software to test the convergent and discriminant validity and the goodness-of-fit indices of the model, which are considered acceptable. The overall goodness-of-fit indices include: Chi-Square/df = 1.084 < 3; GFI = 0.941 > 0.9; CFI = 0.992 > 0.9; TLI = 0.990 > 0.9; RMSEA = 0.015 < 0.8, indicating that the model meets the required analytical standards. After conducting a series of analyses, the model results are presented in Figure 2.

Source: Data analysis results of the authors

Figure 2: SEM results for factors influencing the digital transformation of tourism enterprises

The analysis results in Figure 2 show that the model has a good overall fit, as evidenced by the following fit indices: Chi-Square/df = 1.084 < 3; GFI = 0.941 > 0.9; CFI = 0.992 > 0.9; TLI = 0.990 > 0.9; and RMSEA = 0.015 < 0.08. These fit indices indicate that the model meets the required standards. Table 2 presents the results of the analysis of the theoretical relationships.

Table 2: Hypothesis testing for factors influencing the digital transformation of tourism enterprises

Hypothetical relationship				Standardized Estimate	SE	C.R	<i>p</i>	Results
<i>H</i> ₁	SC	→	DT	0.128	0.106	1.991	0.046	Accepted
<i>H</i> ₂	BG	→	DT	0.200	0.136	3.093	0.002	Accepted
<i>H</i> ₃	CC	→	DT	0.259	0.129	4.029	***	Accepted
<i>H</i> ₄	TP	→	DT	0.232	0.106	3.710	***	Accepted
<i>H</i> ₅	GS	→	DT	0.243	0.097	3.929	***	Accepted

Source: Results from the data analysis by the authors; Note: *** *p* < 0.01.

Table 2 shows that staff capacity (SC) affects the digital transformation (DT) at the 5% significance level. In contrast, business goals (BG), corporate culture (CC), technology platform (TP), and government support policy (GS) have an effect on digital transformation (DT) at the 1% significance level. The standardized regression weights show that corporate culture has the most substantial impact on digital transformation ($\beta = 0.259$), followed by government support policy ($\beta = 0.243$) and technology platform ($\beta = 0.232$). The most minor impact is from staff capacity ($\beta = 0.128$), followed by business goals ($\beta = 0.200$). Moreover, table 2 shows that company culture drives digital transformation the greatest, followed by government assistance policies and technological platforms. Staff capacity and corporate goals are less significant but essential for transformation. By emphasising these elements, tourism companies may navigate the digital transition, improve competitiveness, and sustain industry growth. Finally, improving company culture, government backing, and technology infrastructure while matching business goals and personnel development offers a solid foundation for digital transformation. This strategy positions tourist businesses to thrive in a digital and linked world.

Discussion of Findings

The study findings show that staff capacity impacts the DT process. Employee competence plays a crucial role in successfully implementing digital technologies. Highly competent employees typically understand technology and can quickly adapt and apply it. This result aligns with Khin and Ho (2019), which shows that investment in training employees' digital skills is a key factor for the success of DT, enabling enterprises to quickly access and effectively leverage new technologies.

Business goals significantly impact DT within the research model, indicating that clear business goals are an essential driving force in the DT process. This finding aligns with Kimbu et al. (2023), who assert that specific DT goals help guide and streamline related activities and processes, leading to more consistent and effective implementation (Parvez et al., 2022). Corporate culture is also a critical factor that positively influences DT. A work environment encouraging creativity and technological innovation facilitates employees' adaptation to new technologies. According to Wang et al. (2024), a corporate culture that supports technological innovation helps businesses more easily adapt to digital changes.

Modern technology platforms are a decisive element in the DT process. Enterprises must invest in technological infrastructure to ensure the effective deployment of digital technologies. This result is consistent with Gerhart and Feng (2021), which shows that investing in modern information technology systems is a prerequisite for successful DT. Finally, government support policies drive DT (Singh et al., 2020). Financial support, human resources training, and technology infrastructure provision help enterprises overcome challenges and capitalise on opportunities arising from DT. This finding aligns with Parvez et al. (2022), who emphasise that government support, such as funding programs and training, helps small and medium-sized enterprises overcome difficulties and succeed in digital transformation.

Key elements such as business goals, corporate culture, technology platforms, government support policies, and staff capacity all significantly impact the digital transformation of tourism enterprises (Rousseau & Have, 2022). Among these, business goals, corporate culture, technology platforms, and government policies have the most significant influence. This underscores that the success of digital transformation does not rely on a single factor but results from the coordinated interaction of multiple factors (Bhardwaj et al., 2021). These findings help tourism businesses better understand the drivers and barriers in the digital transformation process (Chanas et al., 2019). This understanding enables them to optimise development strategies to ensure sustainability and competitiveness in an increasingly digital world. Furthermore, the detailed identification of the impact of each factor will facilitate the optimization of digital transformation implementation in the tourism industry of Ho Chi Minh City. It is expected that the digital transformation process in tourism enterprises will be accelerated, contributing to the sustainable growth and prosperity of the industry in the future.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research results have clarified the digital transformation (DT) process of enterprises in the tourism sector of Vietnam, particularly in Ho Chi Minh City. The study identified the most influential factors affecting this process, including staff capacity, business goals, corporate culture, technology platforms, and government support policies. Each of these factors has a significant positive effect on the DT process, contributing to the success of enterprises in adapting to the modern digital environment. In line with broader trends, the tourism sector actively engages with and participates strongly in all aspects of digital transformation. DT requires managers and staff to enhance their digital knowledge to meet strategic, managerial, and operational demands. The digital transformation process in the tourism sector accelerates activities, making them faster and more flexible, leading to a growing demand for skilled labour. Tourism enterprises' staff must be enthusiastic, adaptable, and willing to take risks. Finally, the study has provided a detailed and clear view of the factors affecting the digital transformation in the tourism sector and the implications of the results for economic development. Based on the results, the authors offer the following policy recommendations. These factors, prioritized based on impact, provide actionable insights for driving sustainable digital transformation.

(1) Improving corporate culture: Corporate culture significantly impacts digital transformation ($\beta = 0.259$). A culture of invention and collaboration is essential for digital transformation. Companies should reward innovation and foster a digital integration dialogue. An innovation challenge can encourage employees to suggest innovative solutions, while town halls enlighten

and engage them in the company's digital transition. Mentorship programs can also help older and junior employees adapt to technology, easing cultural change. Finally, this approach requires transparency and communication. Digital transformation leaders should address concerns and provide regular updates. Collaborating platforms like Slack or Microsoft Teams in daily operations will instill a tech-driven culture.

(2) Leveraging government assistance programs is the second most influential factor ($\beta = 0.243$). Tourism companies must actively seek government subsidies and training. Dedicated grant monitoring and application teams can maximise access to these resources. Enterprises can speed digital adoption with technical skills and infrastructure from public-private partnerships. Businesses must advocate for favourable policies like tax incentives and streamlined compliance rules with industry associations. These activities will help SMEs overcome financial and logistical digital transformation challenges.

(3) Investing in sophisticated technology platforms is crucial for digital transformation, having an enormous impact ($\beta = 0.232$). Enterprises must invest in scalable, secure infrastructure to operate. Cloud options like AWS or Azure offer flexibility and reliability for data management. APIs can also provide easy system integration with new technologies. Finally, data security and privacy are crucial in the digital age. To protect client data, businesses should use end-to-end encryption and multi-factor authentication. AI and big data analytics tools can provide actionable insights to improve customer interaction and predict trends.

(4) Aligning company goals with digital strategies is crucial for digital transformation ($\beta = 0.200$). Integrating these aims with digital activities fosters innovation cohesion. Companies should create a strategic roadmap showing how digital tools will help them achieve long-term goals like market share or customer happiness. These projects need KPIs to monitor success. Online booking growth and client retention rates demonstrate progress. Regular evaluations help companies to adjust outcomes-based strategies for ongoing improvement and market alignment.

(5) While building personnel capability has the lowest impact ($\beta = 0.128$), it is nevertheless a crucial aspect of digital transformation. Companies should prioritize upskilling their workers with digital tools and trend training. Employees may help transform the company with digital marketing, data analytics, and IT security certifications. Finally, hiring digital expertise is crucial. Hiring data scientists and designers can boost innovation and expertise. To keep this talent, companies should offer career advancement and mentorship programs that encourage growth and engagement.

Limitations and future research: The study exclusively examined Ho Chi Minh City tourism firms, which may limit its applicability to other regions or industries. Convenience sampling may bias responders because they may not reflect all tourism firms. Additionally, the study uses a cross-sectional strategy to collect data simultaneously. This makes it challenging to track digital change over time or under different economic conditions. Future studies should focus on longitudinal studies to understand digital transformation dynamics and uncover long-term trends and implications. Geographic extension can be performed by extending the survey to additional cities or areas, locally and internationally, to examine digital transformation characteristics in different

contexts. Finally, explore how competition, customer expectations, and global technical improvements affect digital transformation.

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